

Parachor and the Structure of Formic Acid.

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Various structures have been proposed from time to time by different investigators for formic acid and the formates. Recently a paper has been published (Halasyam, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 813) in which the structure of formic acid as proposed by Ray and Sarkar (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1935, p. 109; *cf.* also Ray, *Nature*, 1934, **133**, 646) was supported by Halasyam from the standpoint of the parachor evidence. The object of the present paper is to analyse the arguments of Halasyam and to propose a structure for formic acid from the parachor evidence.

In calculating the theoretical parachor of formic acid, Halasyam adopted the values of Mumford and Phillips for the atomic and the structural constants on the plea that these are improvements on the older values of Sugden. The Mumford and Phillip's method of treating the parachor appears to possess no particular advantage over the system of Sugden and its application appears to be much more complicated. Although it is very probable that Sugden's parachor values may have to be modified in the future, and that further structural equivalents may need to be introduced, there is no doubt that this method of calculating parachors is so simple and the results it has already given are so useful that there appears to be particularly no advantage in replacing it by Mumford and Phillip's system. Moreover in order to prevent confusions and complications, it is better to have a standard, instead of having two different sets of constants. The present author is of opinion that so long as far more convincing results are not obtained by the new system, the use of Sugden's system must be retained, which appears to be the opinion of the majority of the investigators working in this direction. Halasyam has also neglected the very important factor, when adducing the parachor evidence for the structure of formic acid, that the molecules of formic acid are slightly associated. Thus it is apparent that the proof given by Halasyam from the parachor evidence, in support of the structure of formic acid, as suggested by Ray and Sarkar, has practically no weight.

In the present paper the surface tension and density of formic

acid (Kahlbaum's extra-pure reagent further purified by repeated distillation) were determined at different temperatures and the parachors calculated. It will be observed from the results given in the following table that the parachor increases as the temperature is increased indicating that the molecules are associated to a slight extent (*cf.* Sugden, "The Parachor and Valency", 1930, p. 165). The value at 100° (*i.e.*, 95.5) has been obtained from the graph drawn by plotting the parachor against the respective temperature, and it may be assumed, without much error, that the molecules exist mainly in the non-associated state at this temperature, (the b. p.) and that the value 95.5 thus obtained is the correct value of the non-associated formic acid molecule.

TABLE I.

Temp.	Density.	Surface tension.	Parachor.
0°	1.245	40.38	93.70
30	1.208	37.18	94.04
50	1.181	34.65	94.48
75	1.153	32.18	94.97
100	—	—	(95.50)

The calculated value for the structure proposed by Ray and Sarkar,

is 99.0, on the Sugden system. The difference between the theoretical value and the value at 100°, *i.e.*, 3.5 units is much greater than the experimental error. The only reasonable structure consistent with the observed parachor appears to be the following :

However it must be admitted that in this case any particular structure can not be accepted simply from the parachor evidence, as the difference in the parachor value between the possible structures are not sufficiently large to arrive at a definite conclusion.